

Normal School for Teacher Training in Colonial Bengal : A Critical Study

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ABSTRACT : Teacher training in Bengal in modern period was shaped by the British in India with modern perspectives. They promoted normal schools and arranged training for existing pundits, gurus and teachers in different presidencies to improve the qualities of teaching. Different committees were instituted to look in to the system of teacher education and training. Of them Wood's Dispatch, Government of India's Resolution on Education Policy of 1904, Saddler and Hartog Committees made substantive recommendations which hold good for the present times too. School inspectors also suggested positive recommendations to systemize the teacher training system. The present study tries to examine the process of development, growth, origin and major key features of teachers' training system, particularly normal school system in colonial Bengal. Besides exploration of the archival documents, letters, gazetteers and other literary sources have been used in the present study to reach at specific conclusions. It would describe why and when teacher training was established as a system of education in India. Furthermore, it would identify the forces that shaped and developed the teacher training in Un-divided Bengal.

Keywords : Teacher training, Bengal, Normal school, Guru Training, Pundit Training.

I. Introduction

The history of teacher training in Bengal had developed in many phases and levels. During the pre and early colonial period mainly 'monitorial' system was followed to train teachers. In this system quite older and meritorious children were assigned to teach the juniors in the same class or at least some lower

classes. The monitorial system was also known as pupil- teacher system. Though this system was too 'inexpensive' it failed to upkeep positive and progressive impact on training system as a whole. These systems ultimately lead to follow 'rote teaching' (Sengupta, 2011) methods such as parrot like 'sing-song' (Nath, 1968). The 1854 Despatch referred to England's experience in

improving the professional and technical skills of the school teachers. Lord Stanley, the first Secretary of the State, gave stress in his Despatch (1859) upon formal teacher training. The plan involving pupil-teachers and Normal schools, said the writers of the despatch, 'appears to us to be capable of easy adaptation to India' (Richey, 1922). This was a typical view of the pre-1857 which associated the problems of the colony with those of England. Another expression during this period in the same despatch was that the need to improve the teachers working in indigenous vernacular schools or institutions was utmost urgent. They stimulated to attend to Normal schools, to acquire 'professional' abilities to teach in schools. To fulfil this particular objective the Despatch recommended for 'grant-in-aid' and 'stipend'. The Court of Directors which wrote the despatch mentioned its plans for teacher training in the same breath in which it talked of medical and engineering education (Kumar, 2013). The practical purpose of these specialized trainings apart, the symbolic aim was to exhibit that 'industry and ability' were rewarded under English rule. As a consequence of this Despatch (1854) Normal schools were almost started to be established in a vast way over different parts of Bengal. Mainly the venture was undertaken by different missionary agencies, British Government and educated and enlightened native Bengali 'baboo's.

To answer what factors led to the establishment of the training system in Bengal in a nutshell is not so easy, but we may try to pinpoint some events which could be said to be responsible for the said development:

Firstly, employees of the East India Company and people of various missionaries had

established and opened schools particularly for the Eurasians and generally for natives in India and a good number of schools were rapidly established in Bengal and other parts of India before and after 1850's. But who would be the teachers in those newly set up schools? Who will teach in those institutes? The situation demanded to import teachers from Europe. But these practices were too expensive and these conditions had created an environment to made teachers in the soil of India. As a result many normal schools were established after 1850s in Bengal as well as others parts of India.

Secondly, in England compulsory elementary education act was introduced in 1870 and the recommendations of this act was also applicable in the colonies and dependencies of Britain. One of the major recommendations of the said act was that teachers must have a certificate of training. Naturally being a dependency of Britain the demand rose to actualize the recommendations of the said act.

Thirdly, it was logically felt in the words of Stow, 'the gardener, the joiner, the jockey, the artisan must all be trained, and yet at that period it was never thought necessary to train the schoolmaster' (Stow, 1853, P-10).

Etymologically 'normal' school meant certain 'norms' or common 'rules' which were firstly instituted in Normal Seminaries in Great Britain for the training of the school masters.

Mainly three types of normal schools were existed at that time- Government, aided, and privately managed but inspected by the Government. The minimum eligibility for admission in teacher training programmes in normal schools was so low that even a candidate who failed to pass at primary level even could

have been admitted there. Normal Schools had two departments –

1. Guru Training (GT) department (gurus were the teachers in primary schools),
2. Pundit Training (PT) department (middle vernacular school teachers generally called as pundits).

These experiments (GT & PT) were initiated in Bengal during 1885. Under this scheme selected headmasters were authorised to open classes for instruction to the gurus of indigenous primary schools. Both departments had separate staff. The duration of guru training was one year and of the pundit training was three years. The course of study of Guru training was comprised of language, grammar, geography, history, geometry, arithmetic, art of teaching, mensuration (a branch of mathematics that deals with the measurement of areas and volumes of various geometrical figures), dictation, letter writing and on the other hand for Pundit Training Mathematics, Sanskrit, Grammar, History, Physical Geography, Arithmetic, Geometry, Art of teaching, Natural philosophy, Mensuration, Dictation and Composition and use of globe had to be studied (Progress of Education in Bengal, 1864 -65, p-87).

And again the normal training schools could be branched from another perspective into two types. Firstly, the better type of institutions where, the candidates admitted after passing the middle vernacular examination and could be teachers in vernacular secondary schools or headmasters in vernacular schools. The second type of institutions required lower qualification and the pass outs could be ordinary teachers in primary schools.

In 1873 the Lieutenant Governor of Bengal prompted to have training schools for primary school masters in each district for giving a ‘good grounding in surveying and practical sciences’. He also suggested that each normal school must be attached to a model school or pathshala to serve as a practising school for the pupil-teachers (Proceedings, 1873 August). As a result Bengal immediately obtained ten higher normal schools, one for each division except Chooch Behar and Chota Nagpore and one extra for Trihoot and Bihar districts. The sites of these schools were as follows (Proceedings, 1873 August)-

1 Hooghly	6 Patna
2 Calcutta	7 Trihoot
3 Dacca	8 Bhaugulpore
4 Chittagong	9 Cuttack
5 Rampore Beaulah	10 Gwahatty

And again, there were second grade normal schools in the districts where first grade normal schools were not provided and where the population of the districts exceeded a million. The sites of these second grade normal schools were twenty one in number as follows,-

1 Burdwan	11 Sylhet
2 Midnapore	12 Tipperah
3 Nuddea	13 Gya
4 Jessore	14 Mymensing
5 Moorshidabad	15 Shahabad
6 Dinajepore	16 Sarun
7 Rungpore	17 Chumparun
8 Pubna	18 Hazareebaugh
9 Furreadpore	19 Monghyr
10 Bachergunge	20 Purneah
21 Maunbhoom	

There were also third grade normal schools for the smaller districts where the population was less than a million; namely-

1 Bancoorah	8 Poree
2 Beerbhoom	9 Balasore
3 Maldah	10 Singhboom
4 Bograh	11 Goalparah
5 Jalpaigoree	12 Nowgong
6 Cachar	13 Sebsaugor
7 Noacolly	14 Lukimpore

Total cost of this scheme was as follows -

Rs.	
10 First grade normal schools.....	59,400
21 Second grade normal school.....	60,480
14 Third grade normal school.....	27,720
Total =	1,47,600

The Calcutta patshala and other model schools were attached to normal schools as there practising schools. The Patna normal school was the only institution where English was taught but in Bengal, pupils of normal schools were leaving after completion of the only ordinary university course in mother tongue. The Inspector of Schools, Behar Circle strongly recommended that English teaching at normal school be extended, but the medium of instruction should be the vernacular only, namely (Proceedings, 1873, August) -Bengali in Bengal, Hindi in Bihar, Orya in Orissa and Assamese in Assam.

The Indian Education Commission (1882) made categorical recommendations for the training of-

- I. Indigenous school masters to encourage them to undergo training and to bring their relatives and probable successors under regular training.
- II. Candidates eligible for guru training in middle schools as the third grade training schools were found expensive.

As a result of these recommendations a third grade normal class was attached to the vernacular school in Angul in 1883 and an elementary training school was opened at Joypur in 1901. Another measure was taken in 'sessional school' to improve subject knowledge which were started at Berhampur, Aska etc., and the committee opined that the course of instruction should be provided 'out of school time' or in the 'vacation' for existing teachers and every facilities and arrangements should be given to make them attractive for the teachers. But by 1902 they were closed down for lack of students (General Report on Public Instruction in Bengal 1883-84). These types of schools used to remain closed for some months during rice season and reopened again when the labour of the pupils could be spared from the fields. Generally schools remained closed from the middle of June to October, the traditional vacation time of Bengal as well as India and during that time teachers, Gurus, Pundits were normally free from every day to day teaching works.

Special arrangements were made for the education of Mahomedans and Santal children and special school was established at Bhimpore in 1884 by the Wesleyan Mission (American Baptist Mission) for the training of Santal teachers (Proceedings, 1885, September).

On the 11th May, 1863, the first normal training school of mistress was opened at Dacca. Sixteen women were admitted, one of whom was a Brahmini, one Kayasto, two Christians and the rest (eleven) Byrageenees (Proceedings, 1863, July, p-65). The main objectives to pursue the teacher training course at that level were generally –

- 1) to employ herself in a respectable professions in a nearby school,
- 2) to become zenena teacher in their own village or among their friends (Proceedings, 1871, October, p-3).

There was another female normal school in Calcutta, established in 1869 as a department of Bethune school. The Indian Mirror dated 7th April of 1869 raised a question as to where the native students to be found? Baboo Kesub Chundra Sen proposed and promised to send twelve students but could not send any, though he had repeatedly been asked to do so. On the contrary he had started a normal school of his own and he liked to keep the management of things in his own hands. After trial for two years Bethune Normal school had to be closed down.

Honourable Lord Hardinge wished to open special model school and colleges where special training might be given to grown-up girls and young married women. Hardinge observed that the great hope and aspiration the Indian ladies cherished were that a system of education for the girls and women of India should be so developed under the beneficent rule of the British Government that they might have “the power to see clearly, the power to imagine vividly, the power to think independently and power to will nobly” (F-4B/24P-1916). He also wanted the hand, the heart, the head of Indian girls and

women be evenly and harmoniously cultivated so that they might all discharge the duties with grace and efficiency as to whatever situation of the life they were thrown into, whether as wives, or mother, or responsible member of the society. So it was also felt that to acquire the professional teaching skills was not enough for the women, rather they were also to learn through curricula all that concerned ‘enlightened mothering, a good standard of material physique, better care of infancy, appropriate feeding, care and management of children, effective attention to children’s diseases and generally their physical condition, good sanitary environment and other matters of domestic’ (File-4B/24P-1916, p-21).

In June 1863, an Agricultural class was opened in connection with the Calcutta Normal School, taught by Babu Harimohun Mookerjee. The subject of study in this class comprised of “Elementary Botany, Agriculture and Horticulture illustrated by the exhibition of specimens” (Adam, 1968, p- 37). These manual of practical agriculture helped the masses to prepare and give a description of the soils of Bengal, their peculiarities, the means of their improvement or the preservation of their vitality, the crops adapted to the soils, the advantages of drainage and irrigation which led to the principles of practical chemistry; in short, such ideas about Agricultural arrangements and the management of cattle as might be easily comprehensive to the masses, and the practical application of which might be beneficial to the country.

In 1873 H.L Harrison, Vice-President of the District Committee of Midnapore proposed an elaborate scheme to reconstitute the training school and to engraft the technical and other departments of normal schools into the guru

training classes with facilities for technical education, medicine, surveying, carpentry, tailoring and agriculture. He thought that it would be very useful to the gurus and other pupil-teachers. He induced the normal trainees to be trained as native doctors, carpenters, compounders, vaccinators or even tailors and *ameens*, so that gurus will advise and guide to change the pupil's career in a positive way empowering them to opt for a suitable occupation. He was highly ambitious and his intention was to prepare a model training system and 'model guru' who had a little bit of knowledge in every sector and who will play multiple roles in the school and for different class of society in his neighbourhood (Proceedings, 1873, September, p-193). He opined that every teacher must have a lesson on health and the knowledge of the use of quinine and simple drugs. He recognised that the absence of these features were the 'chief error' of previous attempts to promote the primary education. After the experiments for a shorter time this scheme was rejected due to the excrescences and bad effect to hold out to the 'scholars' of normal schools to adopt other professions than teaching.

Conclusion

In this present study, an attempt has been made to examine and evaluate the historical development of teacher training system with reference to normal schools in colonial Bengal. It's true that during the last 100 years or so, the various all-India commissions and committees that were appointed to recommend measures for improving the existing teacher education system proposed and brought enormous changes but all those measures, if considered in the light of the development of teacher education during colonial Bengal, would appear to be 'old wine in

new bottle'. Given to NCTE's dictum during the last two decades, we have incorporated and imported some new terminologies and seemingly new thoughts and all those actions made us stand before the following questions: How far have the existing teacher education institutes served the needs and requirements of teachers as we proposed earlier? Could we adopt the grade-wise three tier training system at primary, elementary and secondary levels? Could we set up a model training centre and produce 'model teachers' who would play pivotal and multiple roles in schools? Could we uphold the standard of teacher education to such an extent so as to imagine of teacher who can't teach well only because of not having a degree in teacher education? Could our teacher education system in recent years produce passionate teachers at school levels?

If we deeply and seriously study the development of training system for teachers in India during the colonial period, we can easily identify and see the existence of almost every component of training programme like insertion of art education, drama education, art of teaching, extending the durations of two years study, long duration of teaching practice in the name of internship in our previous journey (in colonial Bengal) also. Hence, we need to dive deep into the history of teacher education in British India vis-à-vis Bengal for the sake of identifying the forces responsible for creating challenges and prospects of teacher education at their roots.

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